

**O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI OLIY TA’LIM, FAN VA
INNOVATSIYALAR VAZIRLIGI
O‘ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI TRANSPORT VAZIRLIGI
TOSHKENT DAVLAT TRANSPORT UNIVERSITETI**

**“TURKIY DAVLATLARNING O‘ZARO MANFAATLI
INTEGRATSIYASI – BARQAROR TARAQQIYOT
KAFOLATI”**

II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya

MATERIALLARI TO‘PLAMI

Toshkent, 2025-yil 2-3-may

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UDK:

**“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot
kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plami**

“Turkiy davlatlarning o‘zaro manfaatli integratsiyasi – barqaror taraqqiyot kafolati” II xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferensiya to‘plamida jami 94 ta ilmiy maqola kiritilgan bo‘lib, mazkur maqolalar Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi iqtisod, siyosat, madaniyat, turizm sohalaridagi hamkorlik va imkoniyatlar, Barqaror kelajak uchun suv resurslarini boshqarishda iqlim o‘zgarishining roli, o‘rta asr Markaziy Osiyo allomalari ilmiy merosining uchinchi renessans poydevorini barpo etishdagi ahamiyati, Turkiy davlatlarda transport, muxandislik kommunikatsiyalari, energetika, logistika, turizm sohalaridagi integratsiya jarayonlari, Turkiy davlatlar o‘rtasidagi raqamli transformatsiya, fan, ta‘lim va innovatsion rivojlanish istiqbollari kabi yo‘nalishlarni ilmiy jihatdan ochib berilishiga qaratilgan. To‘plamda o‘zbek, rus, ozarbayjon, ingliz tillarida tayyorlangan maqolalar mavjud. Ushbu konferensiya to‘plamidan transport, iqtisodiyot, falsafa, pedagogika va tarix yo‘nalishidagi tadqiqotchilar keng foydalanishi mumkin.

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INCLUSIVE EDUCATION IN THE NEW UZBEKISTAN: LEGAL FRAMEWORK AND DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT. This article focuses on the fact that the political, economic, social and cultural changes taking place in New Uzbekistan necessitate rethinking the usual views and attitudes towards the problem of people with disabilities. The article argues that the problem of socialization of a person with disabilities is not only one of the important humanitarian problems of our time, but is also of a general humanitarian nature, and therefore it cannot be considered as purely practical or economic. It is shown that today disability is not a problem of one person, but of the entire society as a whole. That is why its solution is one of the priority areas of the state's social policy. In the author's opinion, special attention when studying the problems of people with disabilities should be directed to the analysis of the ongoing legal and actual regulation of various aspects of the protection of the rights of people with disabilities. The article analyzes regulatory documents on the protection of the rights of people with disabilities in Uzbekistan, and pays special attention to state policy in the field of inclusive education.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В настоящей статье сделан акцент на то, что происходящие в Новом Узбекистане политические, экономические, социальные и культурные изменения вызывают необходимость переосмысления привычных взглядов и установок на проблему инвалидов. В статье утверждается, что проблема социализации человека с ограниченными возможностями является не только одной из важных гуманитарных проблем нашего времени, но и носит общегуманитарный характер, и потому её нельзя рассматривать как чисто практическую или экономическую. Показано, что сегодня инвалидность — это проблема не одного человека, а всего общества в целом. Именно поэтому её решение является одним из приоритетных направлений социальной политики государства. Отдельное внимание, при изучении проблем инвалидов, по мнению автора, должно быть направлено на анализ осуществляющегося правового и фактического регулирования различных аспектов защиты прав инвалидов в сфере образования. В статье проведен анализ нормативно-правовых документов по защите прав инвалидов в Узбекистане, отдельное внимание обращено на государственную политику в области инклюзивного образования.

ANNOTATSIIYAE. Ushbu maqola Yangi O'zbekistonda ro'y berayotgan siyosiy, iqtisodiy, ijtimoiy va madaniy o'zgarishlar nogironlar muammosiga nisbatan odatiy qarash va munosabatlarni qayta ko'rib chiqish zarurligiga urg'u berilgan. Maqolada nogironlarni jamiyat hayotiga ijtimoiylashuvi muammosi nafaqat hozirgi zamonning muhim gumanitar muammolaridan biri bo'lib hisoblanadi, balki u umumgumanitar xarakterda bo'lib uni sof amaliy yoki iqtisodiy deb hisoblash mumkin emas. Maqolada bugungi kunda nogironlik bir kishining emas, balki butun jamiyatning muammosi ekanligi ko'rsatilgan. Shuning uchun ham uni hal etish davlat ijtimoiy siyosatining ustuvor yo'nalishlaridan biridir. Muallifning fikriga ko'ra, nogironlar muammolarini o'rganishda ularlar huquqlarini himoya qilishning va tartibga solish tahliliga alohida e'tibor qaratish lozim. Maqolada O'zbekistonda nogironlar huquqlarini himoya qilishga doir me'yoriy hujjatlar tahlil qilinib, inklyuziv ta'lim sohasidagi davlat siyosatiga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Key words: disability, inclusion, inclusive education, protection of rights, social guarantees, social policy.

Kalit so'zlar: nogironlik, inklyuziya, inklyuziv ta'lim, huquqlar ximoyasi, ijtimoiy kafolat, ijtimoiy siyosat.

Ключевые слова: инвалидность, инклюзия, инклюзивное образование, защита прав, социальные гарантии, социальная политика.

INTRODUCTION: In recent years, relations between Uzbekistan and Turkey have reached a new level, a number of important projects aimed at expanding cooperation between the two countries in the field of higher education and science, implementing new initiatives and exchanging experience have been successfully implemented. For example, today, through the efforts of the two countries, an agreement was reached to open a branch of the Yunus Emre Cultural Center at the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature, and a Memorandum of Understanding was signed. In recent years, political, trade, economic, cultural and humanitarian ties between the Turkic states have become increasingly stronger. Their main goal is to further expand and strengthen mutual cooperation in the fields of education, science and innovation, as well as the training of qualified and competitive personnel based on advanced international experience.

METHODS: This research is based on a combination of normative legal analysis and socio-humanitarian interpretation. The author examines official documents, national legislation, and international conventions, while also conceptualizing inclusive education within the framework of social policy and ethical responsibility. The study analyzes how legal reforms reflect changing social attitudes toward disability and inclusion.

RESULTS: On January 24, 2025, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the establishment of the International University of Turkic States (No. PP-240) was adopted. The main areas of activity of this university are defined as:

- training of personnel with higher education for the fields of engineering, construction, logistics, information technology and programming, healthcare, agriculture, food industry, as well as economic and social spheres in accordance with international standards;

- implementation of educational programs jointly with foreign, including leading higher education organizations of Turkey, as well as on the basis of joint educational programs and conducting scientific research;

- establishing cooperation with leading foreign higher education and research organizations in the areas of education and scientific research, as well as academic mobility of students;

- increasing the scientific and pedagogical potential of the teaching staff by organizing their internships and advanced training in prestigious foreign higher education organizations and research centers, and much more.

It is expected that this educational institution will make a great contribution to the further spiritual and scientific development of the Turkic peoples.

However, one of the pressing problems facing society today in both Uzbekistan and Turkey remains the problem of wider implementation of the inclusive education system. This is why the exchange of experience in the development and implementation of an inclusive education system both in Uzbekistan and Turkey is of current interest. It should be noted that, in order to effectively solve this problem, it is not enough to simply identify it; it is necessary to develop and create a legislative basis for all reforms that are being carried out in this direction.

As you know, one of the priority areas of state policy in the country is the implementation of the principle “In the name of the honor and dignity of man.” In New Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to supporting the needy segments of the population, including persons with disabilities, protecting and ensuring their rights, freedoms and legitimate interests, radically improving the state of affairs in the field of preventing discrimination on the basis of disability, early detection and prevention, providing medical and social assistance to persons with disabilities, their vocational training and employment.

The modern state is obliged to provide social guarantees of support to those people who most need it, primarily the disabled. Help in difficult life situations is one of the basic principles of modern society, which in earlier historical periods had a traditional, communal, personalized character. The regulatory documents of modern society place emphasis not only on providing assistance, but, above all, on creating conditions for more active integration of persons with disabilities into society.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan establishes that all citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan have the same rights and freedoms and are equal before the law without distinction of gender, race, nationality, language, religion, social origin, beliefs, personal and social status. Today, the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan is ensured by more than 200 legal acts. Particular attention is paid to the implementation of generally recognized international norms and standards in this area into national legislation.

For example, in recent years, on the initiative of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) has been ratified. It proclaims the rights and fundamental freedoms of people with disabilities, in particular their rights to residence, citizenship, legal protection, education, health, work on an equal basis with others, participation in political, social, cultural life, leisure, recreation and sports, creating the necessary conditions for life support for them and their families, and receiving social protection. Guarantees for ensuring these rights are also defined. The Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities consists of 50 articles and was adopted based on an analysis of the situation of persons with disabilities in the world. The World Health Organization estimates that 15 percent of the world's population is made up of people with disabilities, a number that has now reached 1 billion. It is also important that the Convention was adopted on the basis of an in-depth analysis of the situation of persons with disabilities.

In addition, Uzbekistan joined the Incheon Strategy to ensure real rights of persons with disabilities in the Asia-Pacific region; the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Social Services for the Elderly, Persons with Disabilities and Other Socially Vulnerable Categories of the Population” (December 26, 2016), and the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” (October 15, 2020) were developed and adopted.

These laws enshrine basic principles aimed, first of all, at regulating relations in the field of ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities, ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities, contained in international treaties in the field of human rights. These principles are: respect for the dignity of persons with disabilities, their independence, freedom of choice; non-discrimination on the basis of disability; equality of opportunity in the implementation of human rights and freedoms; respect for the developing abilities of children with disabilities and their right to maintain their individuality; accessibility of facilities and services; involvement of persons with disabilities in the life of society and the state.

It is necessary to emphasize the importance of the provisions of the Law “On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” on the recognition of a citizen as a person with a disability, rehabilitation and habilitation of persons with disabilities and the protection of the health of persons with disabilities, and social assistance to persons with disabilities, which describe in detail the procedure for ensuring the rights of persons with disabilities the educational environment (UNESCO, 2017). One of the key ideas of this approach is to ensure that all children attend school in the public school closest to their place of residence.

Currently, the formation of policy regarding children with disabilities in the field of education, as in other areas, is carried out in the context of a social approach, which has replaced the medical model of disability. Within the framework of the social approach, the problem of persons with disabilities is considered in terms of the relationship between the individual and elements of the social system, focusing on discrimination and exclusion. As a result, a person with developmental disabilities and the success of his social adaptation are influenced by underestimation of his capabilities, stereotypes and prejudices, separate education, difficulties in perceiving information, inaccessible living environment, inaccessible transport, discrimination in employment, and other barriers.

According to the social approach, a person with disabilities should be an equal participant in social relations, to whom society should provide equal rights, equal opportunities, equal responsibility and free choice, taking into account his special needs. This fully concerns providing conditions for children with disabilities to receive education on equal terms with their typically developing peers.

With the gradual introduction of the social approach, the issue of determining the legal status of children with disabilities in the general education system has become urgent.

A significant influence on the formation of legislation in the field of education, including inclusive education of persons with disabilities, was exerted by International legal acts adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations in different years, such as: Declaration on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by resolution 3447 (XXX) of the United Nations General Assembly on December 9, 1975; Standard Rules on the Equalization of Opportunities for Persons with Disabilities, adopted by the United Nations General Assembly on December 20, 1993; Salamanca Declaration of Principles, Policies and Practices in the Field of Special Needs Education and the Framework for Action on Special Needs Education adopted by the World Conference on Special Needs Education: Access and Quality (Salamanca, Spain, 7-10.06.1994); Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, adopted by United Nations General Assembly resolution 61/106 of 12/13/2006.

The social model of disability enshrined in the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which substantiates the possibility and necessity of inclusion, is based on the ideas of the autonomy of the individual, his or her unconditional acceptance in society, providing people with disabilities with full opportunities to participate in public activities, and strengthening their social connections.

At the same time, society must eliminate those physical and social barriers that prevent the full inclusion of disabled people in all social processes. The implementation of the social model of inclusion in educational practice assumes that it is inclusion that can lead to the recognition of the need to create conditions for satisfying the special educational and personal needs of disabled people, a system of their support. For example, according to the provisions of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, the right to inclusive education is subject to gradual implementation. The Convention provides that “each State Party undertakes to take steps, to the maximum of its available resources, with a view to achieving progressively the full realization” of social, economic and cultural rights. These measures need to be aimed at building an inclusive education system that includes accessibility, support, teacher education and awareness raising.

States parties to the Convention must adopt a strategy that not only reviews budgetary allocations but also includes planning for the achievement of inclusive education and monitoring progress towards the full realization of the right to inclusive education. According to Article 24

of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, states that ratify the convention undertake to ensure that persons with disabilities have equal access to primary inclusive education, which is quality and free, as well as to general education in the communities where they live.

FEATURES OF THE INCLUSIVE EDUCATION MODEL

The inclusive education model differs from the traditional one in that it involves the adaptation of the education system to the individual needs and capabilities of the child, and not only the normative requirements for the child's level of development to determine his or her readiness for education in the general education system. This principle is stated in the Salamanca Declaration (Salamanca Declaration, 1994, p. 21, para. 28).

Improving the inclusive education system in Uzbekistan is one of the important areas of state policy; a number of positive changes are being implemented in this area. In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 4860 "On measures to further improve the system of education and upbringing of children with special educational needs" became the legal basis for the actions planned in this direction.

This Resolution approved the Concept for the Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System, as well as target indicators for the development of education for children with special educational needs. This Concept was developed for the purpose of organizing a system of inclusive education, guaranteeing and ensuring the right to education for children with special educational needs.

It should be noted that the goal of developing an inclusive education system is to ensure equal opportunities for education and create the conditions necessary to achieve success in education for all children, regardless of their individual characteristics, previous educational achievements, language, culture, and the social and economic status of their parents. The achievement of this goal is aimed at solving one of the priority tasks - the modernization of educational institutions as instruments of social development, including through the creation of an educational environment that ensures the availability of quality education and the successful socialization of persons with disabilities.

In connection with the regulatory consolidation of inclusive education, opportunities for education in general education organizations for children with disabilities are expanding. For the high-quality organization of inclusive education, legislation defines obligations to create special conditions for obtaining education for students with disabilities in each general education organization. Thus, the introduction of inclusive education is currently one of the main directions of development of the education system at all levels.

CONCLUSIONS: Today, the country is systematically implementing the Development Strategy of the New Uzbekistan in 2022-2026, which also defines and addresses specific target tasks to ensure:

- equal access to education and vocational training at all levels for persons with disabilities, improving the conditions of educational institutions that take into account the interests of children with disabilities, a safe and effective learning environment for all;
- sustainable and productive employment and decent work for all women and men, including young people and persons with disabilities, and equal pay for work of equal value;
- promoting the active participation of all people in social, economic and political life, regardless of disability;
- formation of an effective system of support for persons with disabilities, improving their quality and standard of living, including by improving the system of inclusive education and

employment of persons with disabilities, ensuring their involvement and active participation in the socio-economic life of society, as well as a gradual transition to a social model of determining disability, etc.

In order to strengthen the institutional basis of state social support for persons with disabilities, introduce new approaches to the implementation of modern mechanisms of social protection and medical and social assistance, the Agency for the Development of Medical and Social Services, the Interdepartmental Council for Persons with Disabilities, and the Fund for Support of Persons with Disabilities under the Ministry of Health were created. A system of the Unified Electronic Automated Register of the Elderly, Persons with Disabilities and Other Socially Vulnerable Groups of the Population has been created.

In addition, within the framework of the implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the UN Global Agenda until 2030, the Republic has developed and is implementing National Goals and Objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period until 2030, which indicate further goals and objectives related to the rights of persons with disabilities.

Thus, it can be concluded that the state, by ensuring social security for disabled people, creates the necessary conditions for their individual development, the realization of creative and productive opportunities and abilities by taking into account the needs of disabled people in the relevant state programs, as well as the provision of social assistance in the forms stipulated by law in order to eliminate obstacles to the exercise by persons with disabilities of their rights to health protection, work, education and vocational training, housing and other socio-economic rights, which in turn contributes to their more active involvement in society.

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